

A REVIEW OF ULTRA WIDE-BAND ANTENNAS FOR MICROWAVE IMAGING APPLICATIONS

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Abstract

Microwave imaging, a versatile technology with applications in medical diagnostics, security screening, and non-destructive testing, relies heavily on antennas for high-resolution imaging. This paper focuses on designing and optimizing an ultra-wideband antenna tailored specifically for microwave imaging. The goal is to create an antenna that operates over a broad frequency range, enhancing imaging resolution and penetration depth. Employing innovative techniques such as fractal geometries and metamaterial structures, the design process prioritizes considerations like geometry, materials, and impedance matching. Simulation tools and numerical modeling refine the antenna's performance parameters, ensuring efficiency throughout the frequency spectrum. The research also explores the antenna's impact on microwave imaging systems, analyzing factors like signal-to-noise ratio, spatial resolution, and imaging depth. Practical aspects, including fabrication techniques and material selection, are discussed for potential real-world implementation. This study contributes to advancing microwave imaging technologies, presenting an optimized ultra-wideband antenna poised to elevate system capabilities in diverse applications.

KEY WORDS: Ultra-wideband (UWB) antennas, Fractal antennas, Flexible or textile antennas, Feed antennas, feeding techniques, stacked antennas, Microwave imaging, Tumour detection

1. Introduction

Microwave imaging is a non-invasive medical imaging technique widely employed to visualize the internal structures of both healthy and diseased subjects. Commonly used for clinical analysis, it aids in the detection of abnormalities, particularly in cancer management, bone fractures, and tumor identification. Traditional medical imaging methods, such as X-rays, MRI, CT scans, ultrasound, and positron emission tomography, come with limitations, including high costs, non-portability, and potential health risks due to ionizing radiation.

Microwave imaging, operating in the frequency range of hundreds of megahertz to a few gigahertz, presents itself as an alternative with notable advantages. Utilizing non-ionizing, low-power electromagnetic signals, it minimizes health risks and offers cost-effective equipment. The microwave imaging system comprises a microwave source, a receiver, an antenna array, and a radiofrequency switch, allowing for portability and swift diagnosis in emergencies. Despite challenges, such

as lower spatial resolution, advancements in algorithms and hardware have propelled microwave imaging for applications like brain imaging, breast cancer detection, and joint tissue evaluation. The technique relies on tissue-dependent dielectric contrast for signal reconstruction, employing quantitative and qualitative imaging algorithms to generate informative maps or images.

2. Literature Survey

SECTION I: Research Based On Ultra-Wide Band Antennas

Om Prakash Kumar et.al [1] It emphasizes the significant potential of Ultra-Wideband (UWB) technology in communication and advocates for its further development across diverse applications. The initial section focuses on UWB technology antennas and their applications, ranging from disaster management ground-penetrating radars to medical diagnostics and commercial uses like USB dongles and mobile phones. The emergence of pure UWB antennas in the 3.1 to 10.6 GHz range is discussed in Section 3, highlighting their absence of notches in any frequency ranges. Due to interference from WLAN and WiMAX frequency bands, the concept of notching was introduced in UWB technology. Section IV presents various UWB antenna designs causing notching in different frequency ranges. Finally, Section V introduces reconfigurable antennas in UWB technology, detailing their necessity and advantages over conventional UWB technology. The article concludes by asserting the enduring presence of UWB technology and antennas in this frequency range, aiming to present the evolution, growth, and recent trends in the field.

Shreya Mane et.al [2] discusses various aspects of ultrawide band (UWB) antennas, covering their design factors, traits, and different varieties. It emphasizes the challenges associated with UWB methods, prompting an in-depth investigation as indicated by a literature review. The text notes the diverse antenna structures developed for UWB applications, making antenna design a captivating area of study. The historical contribution of inventors of older, more conventional antennas to the art and science of UWB antenna design is acknowledged. Despite some conventional trade-offs, such as gain versus field of view or antenna size versus efficiency, remaining valid, the impact of unique aspects of UWB operation, such as regulatory restrictions, is highlighted. The passage underscores several significant differences between UWB antenna design and conventional narrowband

design. It emphasizes that the entire design of a UWB system is substantially influenced by a UWB antenna's spectrum and impedance matching capabilities, necessitating a comprehensive approach to system and antenna design

Indumathi Ganesan et.al [3] provided a survey of different fractal geometries for Ultra-Wideband (UWB) applications within the frequency range of 3.1-10.6 GHz, utilizing existing methods. The survey includes a performance comparison of various parameters such as resonant frequency, bandwidth, peak realized gain, dimensions, and feeding methods of the fractal antennas. The satellite communication, Global Positioning System (GPS), Global System for Mobile Communications (GSM), Wireless Local Area Network (WLAN), defence systems, and Worldwide Interoperability for Microwave Access (WiMAX). The article also suggests the potential future use of fractal antennas in 5G technology.

THOKALA LATHA et.al [4] provided a comprehensive review of Ultra-Wideband (UWB) phased array antennas, addressing various applications such as radars, communications, satellites, and 5G. The review identifies key challenges in UWB phased arrays, including issues like grating lobes rejection, low profile, wide-angle scanning, ease of manufacturing, low gain variations, better active Voltage Standing Wave Ratio (VSWR), and the generation of multiple beams.

While some beamforming techniques for producing multiple beams are mentioned, the paper notes that these details are not thoroughly explored. The review covers various existing UWB array antennas, including Vivaldi arrays, all-metal arrays, spiral arrays, sinuous arrays, and coupled arrays. It categorizes Vivaldi arrays, all-metal arrays, and coupled arrays as high gain arrays, exhibiting UWB, wide scan, and good radiation properties. On the other hand, spiral and sinuous arrays are defined as low gain arrays, demonstrating UWB, circular polarization, and good radiation properties but with limited scan performance.

S.NO	Antenna Geometry	Frequency (GHz)		Gain (dB)	Operating band (GHz)	Bandwidth (GHz)	Size (mm*mm)
		F1	F2				
1	Wheel shaped fractal	F1	3.2	2.85	2.9-9.5	6.06 or 105.6 %	32*36
		F2	5.3				
		F3	7.2				
		F4	8.3				
		F5	8.8				
2	Hexagonal tree shaped fractal	F1	3.2	from 1.27 to 6.05	2.5-15	12.5 or 142.85 %	39.6*43.5
		F2	5.4				
		F3	6.8				
		F4	8.6				
		F5	11.4				
		F6	14				
3	Hourglass Shaped fractal	F1	6.1	from 1.27 to 6.05	3.75 - 19	13.46 or 134 %	16.9*14
		F2	9.3				
		F3	13.2				
		F4	14.3				
		F5	17.8				
4	Apollonian fractal	F1	4.5	from 1 to 7.8	3-10	15 or 142.86 %	42*46
		F2	6.81				
		F3	10.8				
		F4	13.5				
		F5	16.1				
5	Diamond shaped fractal	F1	2.04	-	2.05-6.245	3.5 or 130 %	67*50
		F2	3.82				
		F3	4.02				
		F4	5.02				
6	Inner tapered tree shaped fractal	F1	6	Max -4.51 Min1.39	4.3-15.5 GHz	11.51 or 113 %	18.5*92
		F2	7.8				
		F3	9.6				
		F4	11.2				
		F5	12				
7	Fractal leaf Antipodal Vivaldi Antenna	F1	1.3	8	1.3 - 20 GHz	175.58 %	50.8*62
		F2	5				
		F3	7				
		F4	15				

for UWB practice.

TABLE 1.0: COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF UWB FRACTAL ANTENNAS [3]

TABLE 1.1: COMPARISON OF ULTRA WIDEBAND ARRAY ANTENNAS [4]

S.NO	Antenna Array	Advantages	Disadvantages	Applications
1	Tapered Slot Antenna / Vivaldi Array	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Low Profile; ❖ wide bandwidth; ❖ Mechanically and electrically flexible; ❖ Maintain low cross polarization over scan angles. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Integration in vertical is complicated; ❖ Requires external wide-band hybrid/balun; ❖ Phase centre changes with frequency; ❖ Bandwidth limited at higher scan angles. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Wireless communications; ❖ Radars; ❖ Remote Sensing; ❖ Defence applications.
2	Spiral Array	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Multi octave bandwidths; ❖ Circular polarization; ❖ Easy to fabricated. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Not exhibits Linear Polarization; ❖ Limited bandwidth over scanning. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Wideband Communication ❖ Radio Astronomy, ❖ Microwave Direction Finding ❖ Navigation, ❖ Monitoring of the frequency spectrum.
3	Sinuous array	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Multi octave bandwidths; ❖ Dual Circular (RHCP/ LHCP) Polarization; ❖ Easy to fabricated. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Not exhibits Linear Polarization; ❖ Limited bandwidth over scanning. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Sensing applications ❖ Defence Industry

4	Coupled Array	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Low Profile; ❖ Mechanically and electrically flexible; ❖ Maintain low cross-polarization over scan angles. ❖ Higher scanning rates are possible with wide Bandwidth. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Vertical integration is complicated; ❖ Requires external wide-band; ❖ hybrid balun; ❖ Phase center changes with frequency. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Mobile communications, ❖ Commercial applications, ❖ Defence Industry.
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SECTION 2: Research Based on Flexible Antennas

Shehab Khan Noor et.al [5] presents a comprehensive analysis of wearable-based textile antennas, focusing on substrate materials. Through an examination of ten relevant research papers, the authors delve into the characteristics of textile materials, including dielectric constant, thickness, and loss tangent. The review encompasses detailed discussions on material considerations, antenna gain, and the potential for enhanced efficiency through integrated solutions. Tables provide an overview of textile material characteristics and results from previous works. The authors advocate for further analysis and improved characterization of ordinary and conductive textile materials to optimize antenna behaviour. The paper aims to provide new researchers with insights into current on-body and implanted antenna designs, emphasizing the evolving and promising nature of wearable textile antennas in the context of rapidly advancing wireless communication technology.

Bahaa Al Mohammed et.al [6] conducts a comprehensive review of electro-textile wearable tags, specifically focusing on microstrip patch antennas within the body-centric context. The choice of microstrip patch antennas is justified by their effective perpendicular radiation to the planar structure and efficient shielding of the human body with a ground plane. The review extensively examines the vital features of both conductive and non-conductive textile materials employed in the design of wearable antennas. Notably, the paper addresses the Specific Absorption Rate (SAR) to characterize absorption rates and assess the impact of electro-textile design on the human body, emphasizing the importance of statistical cataloguing of human body models in experiments across various locations. The authors underscore the potential of wearable antennas in the rapidly advancing landscape of wireless communication technology, emphasizing the need for appropriate manufacturing techniques. Positioned as a benchmark, the review aims to guide material and technique selection for the design of textile wearable tags in Body Area Networks (BAN), showcasing a high-performance embroidery textile slotted patch design antenna as an illustrative example.

S. Ashok Kumar et al. [7] a Coplanar Waveguide (CPW) fed textile antenna has been developed for wearable applications, specifically targeting the 2.45 GHz ISM Band frequency. The antenna is constructed using a substrate made of jeans fabric with a dielectric constant of 1.6. Notably, the chosen fabric, jeans, offers durability, water resistance, and ease of stain removal. The antenna exhibits a favourable performance, with

a reflection coefficient (s_{11}) of -19 dB at the targeted frequency of 2.45 GHz. This design is particularly suitable for applications in military and border security forces

The utilization of jeans fabric, known for its robustness and stain-resistant properties, adds to the antenna's practicality for wearable technology. Despite its positive performance, it's emphasized that the design and fabrication of this antenna pose significant challenges. The observed radiation patterns remain stable within the frequency band of interest, further enhancing its suitability for diverse applications in challenging environments.

Kai-hong Wang et.al [8] an investigation into a dual-band wearable textile antenna has been conducted, encompassing simulations and measurements of return loss and radiation patterns. The findings demonstrate excellent properties that align with the ISM frequency ranges. The textile antenna proposed in this study utilizes common denim material, and a straightforward method was employed to measure its dielectric constant, resulting in increased measurement accuracy (1.54).

The measured results indicate that even when the antenna is in close proximity to the human body, there is no significant impact on its performance. This suggests that the proposed antenna maintains its functionality effectively in wearable applications. The positive characteristics exhibited by the antenna further underscore its suitability for integration into portable wearable devices.

Pranita Manish Potey et.al [9] the analysis concludes that antennas can be effectively designed using commonly used fabric materials, providing a cost-effective and easily integrable solution into fashion garments. Notably, opting for fabric materials like denim is highlighted as advantageous for creating wearable antennas. Emphasizing the benefits of a lower substrate dielectric constant in minimizing surface wave losses and facilitating efficient wave propagation, the study underscores the significance of selecting low-loss substrate materials to enhance overall antenna efficiency. Furthermore, the analysis notes the impact of variations in relative permittivity within the textile substrate on antenna bandwidth, emphasizing the importance of meticulous consideration and optimization of material properties in the design process. In essence, the study supports the practicality of developing fashion-integrated, cost-effective wearable antennas using readily available fabric materials.

TABLE 2.0: COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF RESULTS OF MATERIALS WITH FOUR DIFFERENT VALUES OF DIELECTRIC CONSTANT [9]

S.N O	Fabric material	ϵ_r	Low	Loss Tan α	Feed Point (mm)	S11	Gain (dB)	BW (Return loss)	Directivity (dB)	Efficiency (%)
1	Cotton	1.60	46*53	0.0400	13.5	-32	3.8	0.097	8.44	35%
2	Polyester	1.90	43*50	0.0045	8.0	-35	6.8	0.040	7.90	76%
3	Cordura	1.90	43*50	0.0098	9.5	-29	5.9	0.50	7.93	64%
4	Lyera	1.50	48*54	0.0093	9.0	-31	6.8	0.048	8.59	67%

SECTION 3: Research Based on Feed Mechanism

Aakash Bansal et.al [10] Upon comparing the four feeding methodologies, which include direct feed at the edge of the patch antenna, it is evident that the signal magnitude at 2.45 GHz is significantly superior in the coaxial feed. A similar comparison reveals favourable results for the inset feed as well. However, the direct feed or Microstrip patch feed does not exhibit an optimal response at 2.45 GHz. This observation underscores that the coaxial feed yields superior output compared to the other feeding techniques.

Moreover, the utilization of an array antenna amplifies the output more effectively than any other feeding technique. The presented array antenna employs inset fed for all the antennas. It can be inferred that incorporating coaxial feeding can further improve the results, contributing to an enhanced antenna design. Multiple Antenna Systems (MSA) are still in the developmental stages, although they have already begun to replace traditional antennas in various applications.

TABLE 3.0: PROPERTIES OF COMMONLY USED DIELECTRIC MATERIALS [10]

S.N O	Material	FR4	RO-4003	RT-Duroid
1	Dielectric constant	4.36	3.4	2.2
2	Loss tangent	0.013	0.002	0.0004
3	Water absorption (%)	<0.25	0.06	0.02
4	Tensile strength (MPa)	310	141	450
5	Volume resistivity (M-Ohm.cm)	8×10^7	1700×10^7	2×10^7
6	Surface resistivity (M Ohm)	$2 \times 9 \times 10^5$	4.2×10^5	3×10^7
7	Breakdown voltage	55KV	-	>60KV
8	Peel strength (N/mm)	9	1.05	5.5
9	Density (kg/m ³)	1850	1790	2200

Mr. Jayesh Pathak et.al [11] conducted a comprehensive comparison among traditional microstrip feed lines, CPW feed lines, and the novel ACS feed line in the context of Ultra-Wideband (UWB) antennas. Notably, CPW feed and ACS feed lines offer the added advantage of seamless integration with existing MMIC technology circuits. Furthermore, the ACS feed

UWB antenna exhibits a more compact size, a valuable characteristic in applications where antenna dimensions are critical. However, it is important to note that the asymmetrical structure of the ACS feed UWB antenna can impact radiation characteristics, leading to an asymmetrical radiation pattern along the E plane at higher edge frequencies.

Despite this limitation, it is noteworthy that all three antenna types conform to FCC regulations for the allocated bandwidth in the UWB frequency band. This compliance positions them as suitable candidates for wireless applications. The paper thus provides insights into the trade-offs and advantages associated with different feed line technologies in the design of UWB antennas.

Chao Li, Yonghua Wang et.al [12] provided an overview of the conventional parallel feed configuration used in microstrip antenna arrays and examines the impact of right-angle bends and cutting on array gain. In response to the challenges associated with the traditional feeding scheme, a novel design is introduced. This innovative feeding approach aims to address issues such as large insertion losses and the complexity of the wiring structure. Simulation results indicate that the new feeding configuration demonstrates higher antenna gain and lower circuit losses compared to traditional forms. Furthermore, as the number of cells increases, these advantages become even more pronounced. As a result, this novel feeding design holds promise for a wider range of applications in future microstrip antenna array designs.

Venkata Lakshmaiah Y, B Roy [13] the incorporation of a slot in an antenna, whether on the patch or ground plane, contributes to its compactness and conformal nature. This slot can be fed by various methods, including the resonator, coplanar waveguide (CPW), coaxial, slot line, or microstrip with appropriate modifications, making it versatile for application in all areas of wireless communication. This study explores the design of a small, low-profile microstrip antenna featuring different fed configurations tailored for diverse applications. The introduction of a slot is observed to enhance the bandwidth of these compact antennas, rendering them more suitable for wideband applications. The report emphasizes the various feeding techniques employed to improve the bandwidth and overall performance of microstrip patch antennas, providing insights into their effects on antenna characteristics.

SECTION 4: Research Based on Design of Stacked Antennas

JOAO R. REIS et.al [14] provided a comprehensive literature review on antenna beam steering using transmit arrays. It begins with an overview of 1D and 2D beam steering concepts using transmit arrays, emphasizing the necessity of varying phase in each transmit array element, akin to phased antenna arrays. The literature review focuses on transmit arrays developed for beam steering, wavefront polarization control, and combined features. Special attention is given to active/reconfigurable transmit arrays, featuring electronically

controlled characteristics through mechanisms like p-i-n diodes, varactor diodes, or MEMS switches.

The comparison various examples from the literature, highlighting unit-cell characteristics such as design layout (FSS, MM, or microstrip patch antennas), frequency of operation, bandwidth, unit/cell dimensions, insertion loss, and maximum steering ranges. Transmit array antennas are positioned as feasible alternatives to traditional beam steering techniques, alleviating complexities associated with phased antenna arrays. Leveraging PCB techniques, transmit arrays promise reduced weight, power consumption, and assembly dimensions, rendering them attractive for diverse applications.

(a)

(b)

FIGURE 1.:(a) Unit-cell design (b) transmit array prototype

for antenna beam steering (images extracted from the work presented in [14]).

Future research directions include exploring methods to increase beam steering ranges using conformal transmit arrays, enhancing angular resolution, polarization control, and beam focusing/defocusing. Designing new reconfigurable unit-cell structures is crucial to address existing limitations in bandwidth, insertion losses, and phase ranges. Transitioning from PCB to System on Chip (SoC) technology and integrating active components vertically to conserve space are also highlighted. Additionally, exploring novel electronic biasing metamaterial designs holds potential for advancing transmit array capabilities.

Beam steering via transmit arrays is recognized as a key enabling technology for achieving high peak data rates in mobile radio channels, particularly in emerging 5G and beyond systems. Future transmit array designs are anticipated to target micro- and milli meter-wave frequencies, emphasizing small form factors, lightweight solutions, and enabling agile beam steering and user tracking algorithms.

SECTION 5: Research Based on Microwave Imaging Based Applications

Md. Zulfiker Mahmud et.al [15] provided a comprehensive review of Ultra-Wideband (UWB) antenna sensor capabilities and their current applications in breast imaging. We extensively examine various Microwave Imaging (MWI) methodologies, discussing their limitations and exploring potential solutions to existing challenges. Our analysis suggests significant advancements in UWB-based MWI, particularly in enhancing early detection of breast tumours through the correlation of human tissue dielectric properties with biological conditions. Despite certain constraints, MWI techniques exhibit promising attributes, indicating their potential as valuable adjuncts to traditional medical imaging modalities. Further refinement of MWI techniques is imperative, and collaboration with commercial entities could facilitate the development of robust MWI systems suitable for clinical settings.

TABLE 4: COMPARISON OF DIAGNOSTIC PERFORMANCE OF DIFFERENT TUMOUR DETECTION TECHNIQUES [15]

S	Modality	sensitivity	specificity	Positive predictive value	accuracy	advantages	limitations
1	Mammography	67.8% (120/177)	75% (61/81)	85.7%(120/140)	70.2%(181/258)	Low cost	False positive and negative diagnoses
2	Mammography and clinical examination	77.4% (137/177)	72% (58/81)	85.7% (120/140)	75.6% (195/258)	Low cost	Lower accuracy
3	Clinical examination	50.3% (89/177)	92% (75/81)	58.6% (137/160)	63.6% (164/258)	Simple and easy process	Small tumor cannot detect
4	Ultrasound	83% (147/177)	34% (28/81)	94% (89/95)	67.8%(175/258)	Better than X-ray	Difficult to detect deep-lying or solid tumor
5	Mammography and ultrasound	91.5% (162/177)	23% (19/81)	73.5% (147/200)	70.2%(181/258)	Cost effective	Exists unwanted compression

6	Mammography ultrasound and clinical examination	93.2% (165/177)	22% (18/81)	72.3% (162/224)	70.9% (183/258)	Good candidate for detection	Complex signal processing
7	MRI	94.4% (167/177)	26% (21/81)	72.4% (165/228)	72.9% (188/258)	Provide high resolution images	Higher cost and time-consuming process
8	Mammography, clinical examination, and MRI	99.4% (176/177)	7% (6/81)	70.1% (176/251)	70.5% (182/258)	Best solution ever found	Complex procedure, higher cost and time-consuming process

Jorge A. Tobon Vasquez et.al [16] focuses on employing microwave technology for brain stroke imaging, particularly addressing the challenge of monitoring patients post-stroke onset. The aim is to equip clinicians with a tool for assessing the effectiveness of administered therapies during the follow-up period. The paper introduces a novel prototype characterized by a low-complexity architecture. The device utilizes a minimal number of strategically positioned and designed antennas mounted on a helmet. It operates on a differential imaging approach and generates 3D images of the stroke. Initial experiments involving a 3D phantom filled with brain tissue-mimicking liquid validate the technology's potential in imaging a spherical target resembling a stroke with a radius of 1.25 cm.

Pindi Kiran et.al [17] highlights an alternative medical imaging technique known as microwave imaging, which utilizes non-ionizing electromagnetic (EM) waves for imaging purposes, unlike ionizing x-rays. Microwave imaging equipment is characterized by its low cost and ease of maintenance, in contrast to the expensive and high-maintenance equipment associated with other imaging modalities such as MRI. Numerous research studies have demonstrated the feasibility of employing microwave imaging for various medical applications, including brain stroke and tumour detection, breast cancer screening, heart imaging, and bone imaging.

TABLE 5: COMPARISON FOR DIFFERENT MEDICAL IMAGING TECHNIQUES [17]

S.NO	Imaging techniques	Frequency range	Radiation safety	Image resolution	cost
1	X-ray	3×10^{16} to 3×10^{19} Hz	High	Low	Low
2	CT scanning	3×10^{16} to 3×10^{19} Hz	Very High	Moderate	High
3	MRI	10 to 300M Hz	Low	moderate	High
4	Microwave imaging	300 MHz to 300 GHz	Low	High	Low

3. CONCLUSION & FUTURE SCOPE

In section 1 The passages highlight the vast and exciting advancements in UWB technology, with research exploring antenna design, applications, and potential future uses. From disaster management radars to medical diagnostics and commercial devices, UWB promises seamless integration across diverse fields. The discussion delves into pure UWB antennas, reconfigurable designs, and unique challenges like regulatory restrictions and system-level considerations. Notably, fractal geometries and UWB phased arrays showcase intriguing possibilities for satellite communication, 5G networks, and radar systems. Overall, this glimpse into the

world of UWB underscores its enduring presence and the remarkable progress this technology continues to make.

In section 2 research on wearable textile antennas is booming, with scientists crafting efficient designs using readily available fabrics like denim. These antennas offer promising integration into everyday clothing, boasting durability, cost-effectiveness, and performance even near the human body. However, precise material characterization and optimized manufacturing techniques are crucial for further advancement in this exciting field.

In section 3 highlight various advancements in antenna feeding techniques and their impact on antenna performance. For traditional microstrip antennas, coaxial and inset feeds demonstrated superior signal output at 2.45 GHz compared to direct feed. Array antennas with inset feeds further amplified the output, suggesting the potential of incorporating coaxial feeding for even better results. In the context of UWB antennas, CPW and ACS feed lines offered advantages like seamless integration with MMIC circuits and compact size, although the ACS feed's asymmetrical structure could affect radiation patterns. A novel parallel feed configuration for microstrip antenna arrays was also proposed to address challenges like high insertion losses and complex wiring, achieving higher gain and lower losses compared to traditional designs. Finally, incorporating slots in microstrip antennas was shown to enhance compactness and bandwidth, with various feeding techniques like resonator, CPW, and coaxial offering versatility for diverse applications. These advancements showcase the ongoing efforts to optimize antenna feeding techniques for improved performance and wider applicability.

In section 4 thoroughly explores antenna beam steering using transmit arrays, emphasizing the necessity of phase variation in each transmit array element, akin to phased antenna arrays. Covering 1D and 2D beam steering concepts, wavefront polarization control, and combined features, the review spotlights active/reconfigurable transmit arrays utilizing mechanisms like p-i-n diodes or MEMS switches. Detailed comparisons highlight unit-cell characteristics, such as design layout, frequency, bandwidth, dimensions, insertion loss, and steering ranges. Transmit arrays are positioned as promising alternatives, leveraging PCB techniques to reduce weight, power consumption, and assembly dimensions. Future research directions include exploring conformal transmit arrays for expanded steering ranges, improving angular resolution, polarization control, and beam focusing/defocusing. Addressing limitations in bandwidth and insertion losses through reconfigurable unit-cell structures, transitioning to System on Chip (SoC) technology, and exploring electronic biasing metamaterial designs are crucial. Recognized as a key enabling technology, beam steering via transmit arrays holds significance for high peak data rates in 5G and beyond, with a future emphasis on micro- and millimetre-wave frequencies and agile beam steering for user tracking algorithms.

In section 5 explores the capabilities of Ultra-Wideband (UWB) antenna sensors in Microwave Imaging (MWI) and their applications in breast imaging. The analysis delves into various MWI methodologies, highlighting advancements in UWB-based techniques for early detection of breast tumours by correlating human tissue dielectric properties with biological conditions. Despite limitations, MWI shows promise as a valuable adjunct to traditional medical imaging. The paper then introduces a low-complexity prototype for microwave-

based brain stroke imaging, emphasizing its potential in monitoring post-stroke patients through a differential imaging approach and 3D imaging generation. The article concludes by emphasizing the cost-effectiveness and ease of maintenance associated with microwave imaging equipment, positioning it as a viable alternative for various medical applications, including brain stroke and tumour detection, breast cancer screening, heart imaging, and bone imaging. Further refinement and collaboration with commercial entities are essential for the development of robust MWI systems suitable for clinical settings.

REFERENCES

1. Kumar, Om Prakash, et al. "Ultrawideband antennas: Growth and evolution." *Micromachines* 13.1 (2021): 60.
2. Mane, Shreya. "Overview on Ultra-Wide Band Antennas." *International Journal of Research Radicals in Multidisciplinary Fields, ISSN: 2960-043X* 1.2 (2022): 35-40.
3. Ganesan, Indumathi, and Paulkani Iyampalam. "A review of ultra-wideband fractal antennas." *2018 Second International Conference on Inventive Communication and Computational Technologies (ICICCT)*. IEEE, 2018.
4. Latha, Thokala, et al. "Review on ultra-wideband phased array antennas." *IEEE Access* 9 (2021): 129742-129755.
5. Noor, Shehab, and Nurulazlina Ramli. "A review of the wearable textile-based antenna using different textile materials for wireless applications." *Open Journal of Science and Technology* 3.3 (2020): 237-244.
6. Almohammed, Bahaa, Alyani Ismail, and Aduwati Sali. "Electro-textile wearable antennas in wireless body area networks: Materials, antenna design, manufacturing techniques, and human body consideration—A review." *Textile Research Journal* 91.5-6 (2021): 646-663.
7. Kumar, S. Ashok, and T. Shanmuganantham. "Design and performance of textile antenna for wearable applications." *Transactions on Electrical and Electronic Materials* 19.5 (2018): 352-355.
8. Wang, Kai-hong, and Jiu-sheng Li. "Jeans textile antenna for smart wearable antenna." *2018 12th International Symposium on Antennas, Propagation and EM Theory (ISAPE)*. IEEE, 2018.
9. Potey, Pranita Manish, and Kushal Tuckley. "Design of wearable textile antenna with various substrate and investigation on fabric selection." *2018 3rd international conference on microwave and photonics (ICMAP)*. IEEE, 2018.
10. Bansal, Aakash, and Richa Gupta. "A review on microstrip patch antenna and feeding techniques." *International Journal of Information Technology* 12 (2020): 149-154.
11. Pathak, Jayesh, and Rekha Labade. "Comparative analysis of microstrip feed, CPW feed & ACS feed UWB antenna." *2017 International Conference on Data Management, Analytics and Innovation (ICDMAI)*. IEEE, 2017.
12. Li, Chao, Yonghua Wang, and Zhimin Zhang. "A feed network of microstrip array antenna." *2017 IEEE 2nd Information Technology, Networking, Electronic and Automation Control Conference (ITNEC)*. IEEE, 2017.
13. Venkata Lakshmaiah Y, B Roy. "A Review on slotted microstrip antenna for different feed." 2023 doi: 10.47904/IJSKIT.13.3.2023.41-43
14. Reis, Joao R., Mario Vala, and Rafael FS Caldeirinha. "Review paper on transmitarray antennas." *IEEE Access* 7 (2019): 94171-94188.
15. Mahmud, Md Zulfikar, et al. "Ultra-wideband (UWB) antenna sensor based microwave breast imaging: A review." *Sensors* 18.9 (2018): 2951.
16. Tobon Vasquez, Jorge A., et al. "A prototype microwave system for 3D brain stroke imaging." *Sensors* 20.9 (2020): 2607.
17. Kiran, Pindi. "Microwave imaging." *algorithms* 7.05 (2020).